

Altering the mobile phase composition to enhance self-disproportionation of enantiomers in achiral chromatography

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ABSTRACT

The influence of mobile phase composition on the efficiency of enantiomer separation by achiral chromatography (ACh) was investigated. The separation was induced by the phenomenon of self-disproportionation of enantiomers (SDE) triggered by their homo and hetero-chiral interactions in an achiral environment. Typically, SDE occurs in apolar mobile phases of weak elution strength, which causes the separation time to extend and the process productivity to deteriorate. To mitigate that effect, we altered the content of a strong solvent (modifier) in the mobile phase by use of a solvent gradient in which the target enantiomer was separated in the presence of the weak solvent, whereas the unresolved mixture of enantiomers was eluted by increasing the modifier content in the mobile phase. This enabled accelerating the solute elution while preserving the separation selectivity. The approach was examined for the separation of nonracemic mixtures of two structurally different compounds that exhibited the SDE effect in ACh, i.e., metalaxyl (MX) and methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide (MTSO). The target compound of the separation was the more abundant enantiomer in the enantiomeric mixture. The process realization was preceded by the determination of the effect of the modifier content on the separation yield for enantiomeric mixtures of MX and MTSO of different enantiomeric excess (*ee*). In the case of MX, yield of the pure target enantiomer varied from 2 %, for the maximum concentration of the modifier, to 45 % for the minimum modifier concentration and the largest *ee* used in the experiments. In the case of MTSO, the yield varied from minimum 40 % to maximum 66 %. To predict the process, we employed a dynamic model, in which underlying thermodynamic dependencies were implemented.

1. Introduction

The self-disproportionation of enantiomers (SDE) can occur in any process of separation of nonracemic mixtures of enantiomers in an achiral environment [1–15]. The SDE phenomenon stems from molecular interactions, such as hydrogen bonding or dipole–dipole interactions which induce formation of homo- and heterochiral associations [1–3]. This results in an uneven distribution of the enantiomers among the isolated fractions.

SDE has been reported for a number of achiral separations of enantiomers by all chromatographic techniques including high and medium pressure liquid chromatography, gravity-driven column chromatography, flash chromatography and size-exclusion chromatography [16–35]. Most of the SDE-driven separations reported were performed using silica-based adsorbents. SDE was showed to occur for different classes of chiral compounds possessing the so-called SDE-phoric groups,

including sulfoxides, CF₃-derivatives, amides, carboxylic acids, amino acids, dipeptides derivatives, alcohols, phenols, esters, heterocycles, etc. [1–3]. Nevertheless, SDE has also been observed for compounds lacking functional groups capable of forming strong molecular interactions [11]. The occurrence of SDE is undesired in the course of quantitative chromatographic analysis, as it can be a cause of misinterpretation of the stereochemical outcome [36–41]. Yet, that phenomenon can be potentially utilized in preparative or industrial separations of nonracemic mixtures for total or partial replacement of chiral chromatography (CCh). CCh is usually a cost driver in manufacturing of pure enantiomers, due to high costs of chiral stationary phases (CSPs) and their limited mechanical stability. Yet, realization of efficient SDE-based achiral chromatography (SDE-ACh) is still far from routine. To make the process applicable in a large scale, the interplay between the separation efficiency and the operating conditions should be quantified. The efficiency of enantiomer separation by achiral chromatography is

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reported to depend on the column loading conditions and the level of enantiomeric excess (*ee*) of the mixtures to be separated [1–3]. Nevertheless, the process variable that is the most critical for the separation selectivity is the composition of the mobile phase. Interactions between molecules of enantiomers and polar solvents are competitive against interactions between molecules of the enantiomers, thus they suppress the SDE effect [40]. However, the presence of a strong solvent, termed as the mobile phase modifier, is often indispensable to elute compounds that are strongly adsorbed on polar silica surfaces. Yet, the literature lacks a quantitative description of that issue, which is indispensable for optimizing the performance of the process and its successful sale up. Therefore, in this study we quantitatively examined the effect of the modifier content in the mobile phase on the efficiency of the SDE-ACH separations of enantiomeric mixtures of different chiral compounds. To accelerate the course of chromatographic elution while preserving the SDE effect, we employed a solvent gradient. In that approach, the target enantiomer is eluted with a weak solvent, whereas unresolved mixture is recovered by increasing the concentration of the modifier in the mobile phase. To quantify the impact of the modifier concentration on the extent of the SDE effect and to design the gradient separation, we employed a dynamic model, in which underlying thermodynamic dependencies were implemented. The model was used to predict the course of gradient elution and the separation yield.

2. Theory

2.1. Adsorption equilibrium

To determine the adsorption equilibrium of enantiomers, we adopted the isotherm model developed in the previous study [35]. It described the SDE effect as a result of formation of enantiomeric associates in a second order reaction. Unlike in several studies reported in the literature [22,42–46], in which the association mechanism was quantified for the liquid phase, we quantified it for the adsorbed phase. Different retention properties of enantiomers in ACh were assumed to stem from the difference in the interaction energies between the adsorbed molecules of the same and the opposite enantiomer. In general, such a mechanism can be classified as so-called positive cooperative adsorption, which occurs due to preferred or multilayer adsorption [47,48]. In the case of preferred adsorption, the solute molecules already present in the adsorbed phase promote adsorption of other molecules on adjacent adsorption sites on the adsorbent surface. The path of the SDE mechanism developed in [49,50] to describe SDE on an achiral Cu surface, can be ascribed to that type of adsorption. In the case of multilayer adsorption, the adsorbed molecules provide additional adsorption sites on their own molecular surface. That model was used in this and the previous study, as it enabled reproducing the overloaded band profiles for enantiomeric mixtures of different chiral compounds.

The adsorption of the enantiomers was assumed to follow the Langmuir-type second order reaction occurring in the first layer on adsorption sites on a bare silica surface (layer *I*), and in the second layer (layer *II*) on additional interaction sites on the surface of the adsorbed molecules of enantiomers. The mechanism is represented by the following set of reaction equations:

- for the enantiomer *i* (*i* = *S*, *R*) interacting with an active site *S** on bare adsorbent surface (layer *I*):

- for the enantiomer *i* (*i* = *S*, *R*) interacting with an active site provided by the molecule of the same enantiomer (homochiral associate):

- for the enantiomer *j* (*j* = *S*, *R*) interacting with an active site provided by the unlike enantiomer (heterochiral associate):

Eqs. (1–3) can be represented by the equilibrium equations defining the adsorption isotherm as follows [35].

For the adsorbed phase concentration of the enantiomer *i* on bare silica (layer *I*), q_i^I , it holds:

$$q_i^I = \frac{q^m K^I C_i}{1 + K^I \sum_i C_i} \quad (4)$$

where q^m is the binding capacity on bare silica, K^I is the corresponding equilibrium constant. Since achiral silica surface recognises enantiomers in the same manner, the values of q^m and K^I for both enantiomers are the same.

For the adsorbed phase concentration of the enantiomer *i*, q_i^{II} , adsorbed in the subsequent layer *II*, it holds:

$$q_i^{II} = \frac{q_i^I K_{hom}^{II} C_i}{1 + K_{hom}^{II} C_i + K_{het}^{II} C_j} + \frac{q_j^I K_{het}^{II} C_i}{1 + K_{het}^{II} C_i + K_{hom}^{II} C_j} \quad (5)$$

where the first term on the right-hand side corresponds to adsorption on active sites provided by molecules of the same enantiomer (homochiral association, Eq. (2)), while the second term to adsorption on sites provided by molecules of the opposite enantiomer (heterochiral association Eq. (3)), K_{hom}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} is the equilibrium constant of binding of the enantiomer on the adsorption sites provided by the molecules of the same enantiomer, and the opposite enantiomer, respectively.

The total adsorption of the enantiomer *i*, $q_{i,tot}^*$, is the sum of Eqs. (4) and (5):

$$q_{i,tot}^* = q_i^I + q_i^{II} = \frac{q^m K^I C_i}{1 + K^I \sum_i C_i} + \frac{q_i^I K_{hom}^{II} C_i}{1 + K_{hom}^{II} C_i + K_{het}^{II} C_j} + \frac{q_j^I K_{het}^{II} C_i}{1 + K_{het}^{II} C_i + K_{hom}^{II} C_j} \quad (6)$$

The ratio of $K_{hom}^{II}/K_{het}^{II}$, which determines the selectivity of the separation, is expressed as:

$$\frac{K_{hom}^{II}}{K_{het}^{II}} = \frac{\delta}{1 - \delta} \quad (7)$$

where δ takes the values between >0 , which corresponds to the theoretical highest resolution, and <0.5 , which corresponds to the lack of the resolution.

For low concentrations, q_i^{II} tends to zero, and Eq. (6) converts to the linear isotherm:

$$q_i^I = H C_i \quad (8)$$

where *H* is the Henry constant:

$$H = q^m K^I \quad (9)$$

The Henry constant is the same for both enantiomers, therefore the separation is possible only under nonlinear isotherm conditions, when the opposite enantiomers can compete for the adsorption sites in the second adsorbed layer.

2.2. Dynamic model

To simulate chromatographic band profiles, the equilibrium-dispersive model was used as follows [51]:

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + w \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} + F \frac{\partial q_{tot,i}^*}{\partial t} = D_{L,a} \frac{\partial^2 C_i}{\partial x^2} \quad (10)$$

where $q_{tot,i}^*$ is the equilibrium concentration in the adsorbed phase in mg of the species i per mL of the solid matrix ($\text{mg mL}^{-1}_{matrix}$) given by the isotherm equation (Eq. (6)), C_i (mg mL^{-1}) is the corresponding liquid phase concentration, t (s), x (m) are the time and spatial coordinates, respectively, w (m s^{-1}) is the interstitial velocity, $D_{L,a}$ (m^2s^{-1}) is the apparent dispersion coefficient, F is the phase ratio: $F = (1 - \epsilon_t) / \epsilon_t$, ϵ_t is the packed bed porosity.

The model is coupled with the boundary conditions corresponding to a rectangular pulse injection at the column inlet (at $t > 0$):

$$C_{i,inlet}(t) = \begin{cases} C_{i,inj} & \text{for } t \in [0, t_{inj}] \\ 0 & \text{for } t > t_{inj} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where t_{inj} is the width of the pulse (the injection time).

The inlet profile of the modifier in the gradient mode is described as:

$$C_{mod,inlet}(t) = \begin{cases} C_{mod} & \text{for } t \in [0, t_{start}] \\ C_{mod} + \lambda(t) & \text{for } t > t_{start} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where C_{mod} is the initial modifier concentration, $\lambda(t)$ defines the shape of the gradient profile; e.g., for the step gradient that value is constant, and for the linear gradient it defines the gradient slope, t_{start} is the start of the gradient, i.e., the time of switching of the solvents composing the mobile phase.

For the concentration profile at the column outlet (at $t > 0$) it holds:

$$\frac{\partial C_i(t, L)}{\partial x} = 0 \text{ for } x = L \quad (13)$$

where L is the column length.

The initial conditions ($t = 0$) correspond to the column free of the sample components.

The model was solved using the forward-backward scheme [51]. In that scheme, the dispersion term in Eq. (10) is accounted for indirectly by adjusting numerical dispersion; the apparent dispersion coefficient, $D_{L,a}$, is given by the following equation:

$$D_{L,a} = \frac{L w}{2N} \quad (14)$$

where N is the plate number that corresponds to the column efficiency.

The space increment, Δx , in the numerical scheme is equal to HETP:

$$\Delta x = \text{HETP} = L/N \quad (15)$$

where L is the column length.

The time increment Δt is calculated from:

$$\Delta t = \frac{2 \Delta x t_r}{L} \quad (16)$$

where t_r is the retention time:

$$t_r = \frac{L}{w} (F H + 1) \quad (17)$$

The solution of Eqs (6, 10–13) provides the concentration profiles of binary mixtures of the enantiomers.

To calculate the migration velocity of the concentration front of the modifier in the gradient elution, Eqs (12) and (17) were combined; in the latter, the column length, L , was replaced with the local value of the space variable.

The algorithm allows very vast simulations of band profiles, even for columns with a very high plate number.

3. Experimental

3.1. Equipment

The Hitachi HPLC system Primade was used to perform chromatographic experiments. The HPLC device consisted of a high-pressure quaternary pump, an autosampler, a thermostat, an interface box and a UV detector.

The polarimetric measurements were performed using the Jasco polarimeter P-2000.

3.2. Materials

Racemic R,S-Metalaxyl (R,S-MX) (Pu > 94 %), R-Metalaxyl (R-MX) (Pu > 92 %) were obtained from Sharda Cropchem Limited (Mumbai, India), R,S-Methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide (R,S-MTOS) (Pu > 99 %), was purchased from Apollo Scientific (Bredbury, UK), S-Methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide (S-MTOS) (Pu > 98 %) was purchased from AmBeed (Arlington Heights, USA). The structure of the compounds is depicted in Fig. 1.

Methyl *tert*-butyl ether (MTBE), isopropyl alcohol (*i*-PrOH), *n*-hexane, dichloromethane (DCM), ethanol (EtOH) with HPLC purity grade, were purchased from Honeywell (Charlotte, USA), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (Pu > 99.5 %) were obtained from Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium).

The SDE-ACh separations were performed using the silica gel column LICHROSPHER® Si 60, 250×4 mm, with the particle size of 5 μm from by Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). The CSP columns used for the fraction analysis were: ReproSil Chiral-MIC, 250×4.6 mm, with the particle size of 5 μm purchased from Dr Maisch (Ammerbuch, Germany), and CHIRALPAK® IC 250×4.6 mm, with the particle size of 5 μm purchased from Daicel Corporation (Osaka, Japan).

Fig. 1. Structures of the model compounds: (A) MX, (B) MTOS.

3.3. Procedures

3.3.1. Chromatographic elution

The solvents for the SDE-ACh separation of the MX enantiomers were selected based on the research performed in the previous study [35]; the mobile phase was composed of mixtures of *n*-hexane and MTBE (the modifier) enabled collection of fractions of pure *R*-MX as the target product.

In this study, the elution of MX was performed in isocratic and gradient modes. In the isocratic mode, the MX enantiomers were eluted using mixtures of *n*-hexane and MTBE with different volume fractions of MTBE, $\varphi_{\text{MTBE}} = 60, 65, 75, 85, 100\%$ v/v. The lower limit of the content of the modifier in the mobile phase was associated with solute retention of ca. 30 column volumes (CV), i.e., ca. 90 min at $Q = 1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$, whereas the upper limit was associated with solute retention of about 5 CV. The column pressure drop varied from 3.4 to 3.7 MPa, depending on the volume fraction of the modifier in the mobile phase.

The gradient elution was created as a step gradient; the eluent containing $\varphi_{\text{MTBE}} = 60\%$ v/v was fed for 18 min, and then it was exchanged for the modifier $\varphi_{\text{MTBE}} = 100\%$ v/v. The mobile phase flowrate for both isocratic and gradient modes was $Q = 1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$.

The nonracemic mixtures of MX with the concentration of $C_{\text{inj}} = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ (in total for both enantiomers) and *ee* for the more abundant enantiomer (*R*) at 30, 50 or 70 % were injected with the injection volume $V_{\text{inj}} = 0.09 \text{ mL}$. The total profiles were recorded using the UV detector at a wavelength of 280 nm.

The ACh effluent was fractionated and analyzed offline by CCh to obtain the concentration profiles of the individual enantiomers in nonracemic mixtures. The CCh analysis of the ACh effluent was performed using ReproSil Chiral-MIC with *n*-hexane/DCM/EtOH (30/70/0.75 v/v) at $Q = 1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$, at wavelength of 230 nm.

The separation of nonracemic mixtures of the MTSO enantiomers by SDE-ACh was preceded by scouting different solvents to find the mobile phase composition which was optimal to isolate pure *S*-MTSO fractions from mixtures.

Eventually, MTBE and *i*-PrOH as the modifier were selected as the constituents of the mobile phase. The isocratic elution of MTSO in SDE-ACh was performed at different concentrations of *i*-PrOH in the mobile phase, $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 0, 1, 3, 10, 15\%$ v/v. The low and the upper limit for the content of the modifier was selected based on the duration of the solute retention, similarly as for the elution of MX.

In the gradient elution, the eluent containing $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 0\%$ v/v was exchanged for $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 25\%$ v/v at 45 min after the sample injection. The flowrate of the mobile phase in both modes was $Q = 1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ or 2 mL min^{-1} . The column pressure drop varied from 3.7 to 4.8 MPa at $Q = 1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ and was doubled at $Q = 2 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$.

Nonracemic mixtures of MTSO with the concentration $C_{\text{inj}} = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ (in total) and *ee* for the more abundant enantiomer (*S*) at 30, 50 or 70 % were injected with the injection volume $V_{\text{inj}} = 0.09 \text{ mL}$. The profiles were recorded at wavelength of 285 nm.

The CCh analysis of the ACh effluent was performed using CHIRALPAK® IC with MTBE/*i*-PrOH (85/15 v/v) at $Q = 1.5 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$. The profiles were recorded at wavelength of 246 nm.

For all ACh separations and the CCh analysis, the detection wavelength was adjusted to ensure the linearity of the detector calibration curve.

All chromatographic experiments were performed at temperature of 23 °C.

3.3.2. Column porosity measurements

The porosity of the ACh column was determined from the elution time of pulses of *n*-hexane in the adequate mobile phase. The total bed porosity obtained after subtracting the contribution of the residence time in extra column volumes was $\varepsilon_t = 0.72$.

3.3.3. Repeatability of the measurements

To verify the repeatability of the elution experiments, a series of chromatograms were repeated four times under the same conditions, but in two subsequent days, each time using freshly prepared mobile phase and sample.

3.3.4. Polarimetry measurements

Weighed samples of the pure enantiomers or the nonracemic mixtures were dissolved in adequate mobile phase for use in ACh. The optical rotation of the samples was measured with the sodium lamp set to 589 nm, with light source parameters: aperture 8.0, D.I.T. 5, cycle 5 times, cycle interval 7 s.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Polarimetry measurements

The possibility of formation of chiral associations of the MX enantiomers in the solvents composing the mobile phase was excluded in the previous work based on polarimetric measurements performed for pure *R*-MX and nonracemic mixtures of *R*-MX and *S*-MX dissolved at different concentrations in the mixtures of *n*-hexane and MTBE [35]. The course of the concentration dependency of optical rotation was linear over a wide concentration range of the enantiomeric solutions. As associates have different optical activity than monomers, their presence perturbs the linear response of the polarimeter [52,53]. Furthermore, the results of the NMR measurements did not reveal differences between the spectra of pure enantiomers and their racemic mixtures.

Analogous results were obtained in this work for enantiomeric mixtures of MTSO (Fig. S1, Supporting information). The analysis of the results obtained also excluded noticeable formation of associates in liquid solutions and indicated that the SDE effect occurred dominantly or exclusively in the adsorbed phase in the contact with silica surface.

4.2. Isocratic elution

4.2.1. Repeatability of the experiments

To verify the repeatability of the elution experiments, a series of chromatograms of the enantiomeric mixtures of MX and MTSO were recorded under the same operating conditions, as reported in Section 3.3.3. Minor deviations between subsequent measurements were observed, which were attributed to a slight instability of the mobile phase flowrate due to small fluctuations in the column pressure drop. This stemmed from the flow behavior of volatile solvents of low density and low vapor pressure. Therefore, the repeatability of the chromatograms varied with increasing concentration of the modifier, the latter having higher density than the weak solvent, which resulted in an increase in the column pressure drop. Typical results of those experiments for MX are depicted in Fig. 2 for different modifier concentrations and the mobile phase flowrates $Q = 1$ or 2 mL min^{-1} , i.e., for a double change in the column pressure drop. A similar result was obtained for MTSO. The repeatability of the elution experiments appeared to be acceptable, however it might be improved by increasing the column pressure drop up to values markedly exceeding the vapor pressure of the solvent mixture used for preparing the mobile phase. This can be achieved, e.g., by assembling a flow restrictor downstream from the detection cell on the backpressure side.

4.3. Dependence of the SDE-effect on the modifier concentration

To determine the influence of the mobile phase composition on the extent of the SDE effect, a series of isocratic elution experiments were performed for nonracemic mixtures of both pairs of enantiomers at different concentrations of the modifier in the mobile phase (3.3.1).

A decrease in the modifier concentration caused enhancement of the SDE effect, which improved the separation selectivity, thus the

Fig. 2. Repeatability of the separation of the MX racemate, $V_{inj} = 0.09$ mL, $C_{inj} = 60$ mg mL⁻¹. A) mobile phase: *n*-hexane/MTBE (40/60 v/v), flowrate $Q = 2$ mL min⁻¹, B) mobile phase: *n*-hexane/MTBE/ (25/75 v/v), $Q = 2$ mL min⁻¹, C) mobile phase: *n*-hexane/MTBE (25/75 v/v), $Q = 1$ mL min⁻¹.

operation yield. This is demonstrated in Table 1, where the yield of the target enantiomer achieved for different modifier concentrations is presented for nonracemic mixtures of MX and MTSO of $ee = 50$ %.

However, the benefit in the selectivity is counterbalanced by increase in the solute retention time, which diminishes the purification rate, thus the process productivity. That effect is illustrated in Figs. 3A-3D and Figs. 4A-4D. As can be observed, for about a threefold decrease in the retention time, the *R*-MX yield reduced by over ten times (Table 1,

Fig. 3), whereas a fivefold decrease in the retention of MTSO corresponded to about a twofold reduction in yield (Table 1, Fig. 4).

The gain in yield depended on ee of the mixture. In all cases investigated, the yield improved with increasing ee . An increase in the concentration ratio between the opposite enantiomers caused that the difference in the chromatographic velocities associated with their ascending fronts increased. This widened the fractionation time of the pure target enantiomer, which enhanced the separation yield. That effect is exemplified in Fig. 5, where the yields obtained for the separation of the enantiomeric mixtures of MX and MTSO of different ee levels are presented.

4.4. Determination of the model parameters

The isotherm coefficients: q^m , K^I , K_{homo}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} (Eq. (6)) were determined by the peak fitting method. In that method, the isotherm coefficients are adjusted in the dynamic model using an optimization procedure to obtain the best match between the experimental data and the model simulations. The experimental basis for the estimation were profiles of nonracemic mixtures of enantiomers recorded under strong overloading conditions, i.e., 60 mg mL⁻¹ and $V_{inj} = 0.09$ mL, which corresponded to 1.7 mg per 1 mL of the column volume or 6.1 mg per 1 mL of the solid matrix volume. All the band profiles selected for fitting were characterized by the sharp ascending concentration fronts, as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Apart from the isotherm coefficients, which quantify adsorption thermodynamics, the apparent dispersion coefficient D_{app} , which lumps kinetic effects, had to be evaluated. The value of D_{app} was determined from the number of theoretical plates, N (Eq. (13)). Nevertheless, the profiles of enantiomers exhibited strong peak tailing, particularly at low modifier concentrations, which rendered the determination of the column efficiency based on the peak shape difficult. This stemmed from the energetic heterogeneity of adsorption on a bare silica surface. Eventually, the N number was used as a supplementary estimation parameter, which was stepwise evaluated over a range of 1000–8000 using steps of 500. The values of the isotherm coefficients were found to depend very weakly on the N number, which is typical for sharp ascending concentration fronts at strong concentration overloading. The fitting procedure was based on a derivative free method, in which a stochastic optimization algorithm was implemented [54]. That procedure prevents trapping the solution in a local optimum. The parameters q^m and K^I determine the retention time and the peak shape under low and medium loading conditions, for which the contribution of the first term of Eq. (6) is dominating. The parameters K_{homo}^{II} and K_{het}^{II} influence the shape of peaks in binary mixtures for high loading conditions; the ratio $K_{homo}^{II}/K_{het}^{II}$ determines the extent of the displacement effect and the separation selectivity.

The calculations were repeated for different modifier concentrations in the mobile phase. $N = 2500$ provided the best fit to the experimental data for MX, and $N = 4000$ for MTSO. To verify the obtained values of the parameters, the model predictions were compared with the experimental data acquired for different loading conditions and the ee levels (an example is shown in Fig. S2, Supporting information).

Typical results of peak fitting performed for the enantiomeric mixtures of MTSO and MX with $ee = 50$ % are superimposed on the experimental data in Figs. 3 and 4. For both chiral compounds, the model did not accurately predict peak tailing resulting from the aforementioned silica surface heterogeneity, which was not accounted for in the isotherm model. Nevertheless, that problem pertained only to the range of very low solute concentrations in chromatographic peaks, at which the SDE effect was not active. The values of the estimated parameters and the courses of their empirical dependencies on the modifier concentration are plotted in Fig. 6, and provided in Table 2. The binding capacity for MTSO was nearly constant, which indicated that within the range investigated the number of active sites available for MTSO was not affected by the modifier concentration. The equilibrium

Table 1

Yield of the separation of enantiomeric mixtures of MX and MTSO with $ee = 50\%$. The yield was defined as the percent ratio of the mass of the target enantiomer in the collected pool of purity of 99 % to its mass in the injected sample.

Component	Target enantiomer	Modifier	% φ (v/v) modifier	Yield% (w/w) (experiment)	Yield% (w/w) (simulation)
MX	R-MX	MTBE	100	1.9	1.5
			85	25.9	16.0
			75	30.7	28.5
			65	33.2	36.1
			60	35.8	32.1
			Gradient from 60 to 100 %	40.4	31.6
			15	40.1	32.4
MTSO	S-MTSO	<i>i</i> -PrOH	10	49.7	49.8
			3	50.0	49.4
			1	51.8	53.1
			0	66.5	66.3
			Gradient from 0 to 25 %	66.9	65.8

Fig. 3. Individual profiles of the MX enantiomers $ee_R=50\%$, $V_{in} = 0.09$ mL, $C_{inj} = 60$ mg mL⁻¹, $Q = 1$ mL min⁻¹, mobile phase *n*-hexane/MTBE: A) $\varphi_{MTBE} = 60\%$, B) $\varphi_{MTBE} = 65\%$, C) $\varphi_{MTBE} = 75\%$, D) $\varphi_{MTBE} = 85\%$, Symbols – experimental data, lines – simulation.

constants, which reflect the energy of the underlying interactions, decreased with increasing modifier concentrations. The ratio K_{het}^H and K_{homo}^H , which defines the extent of the SDE effect, thus the separation selectivity, also decreased with increasing the content of the modifier in the mobile phase. This particularly held true for MTSO, for which that ratio was high at low *i*-PrOH concentrations, and it drastically reduced at the *i*-PrOH concentrations above 4% v/v. As mentioned above, molecular interactions enantiomer-polar modifier are competitive against interactions enantiomer-enantiomer, therefore they suppress the SDE effect [40]. Therefore, the trend observed can be generalized for other

compounds; another example is provided in Fig. S3 (Supporting information).

4.5. Gradient elution

The start of the step gradient, i.e., the time of switching the eluents, was selected in such a way that the fraction containing pure target enantiomer left the column with the weak solvent, whereas the unresolved fraction of both enantiomers was desorbed with the strong solvent. The course of the separation is illustrated in Fig. 7A for MX and

Fig. 4. Individual profiles of the MTSO enantiomers, $ee_s = 50\%$, $V_{in} = 0.09\text{ mL}$, $C_{inj} = 60\text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, $Q = 1\text{ mL min}^{-1}$, the mobile phase MTBE/*i*-PrOH: A) $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 1\%$, B) $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 3\%$, C) $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 10\%$, D) $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 15\%$. Symbols – experimental data, lines – simulation.

Fig. 5. Effect of the ee level of the enantiomeric mixtures on the separation yield.

Fig. 7B for MTSO. The sharp increase in the elution strength caused the fronts of the unresolved fractions to sharpen and concentrate. This markedly reduced the separation time compared with the isocratic mode, which is exemplified in Fig. 7B. To describe the process, the dynamic model was supplemented with the dependencies of the isotherm coefficients on the modifier concentration (Table 2) and used to predict

the experimental separations of nonracemic mixtures of both pairs of enantiomers. The simulation underpredicted peak tailing of the unresolved fraction, for the same reason as reported for the isocratic elution profiles. Yet, the yield of the separation was well predicted by the model (Table 1). Therefore, the model was further used for the prediction of the separation course for different gradient shapes. Examples of the simulation results for the separation of the enantiomeric mixtures of MTSO are shown in Fig. 8 for $ee_s = 50\%$, and in Fig. S3 (Supplementary materials) for $ee_s = 70\%$. In plot I, a linear gradient was used to elute the sample, whereas in plot II the start of the time for the step eluent exchange was adjusted so that the front of the modifier step change coincided with the front of the unresolved fraction. In the latter case, the yield reached maximum, but at long solute retention and strong dilution of the fraction of the target enantiomer. To reduce the retention time, the elution strength of the mobile phase can be changed gradually using linear or nonlinear gradients. This results in compressing the solute peaks, but at the expense of yield reduction. Yet, by proper selection of the gradient shape the yield reduction can be mitigated. In the linear gradient illustrated in Fig. 8, the elution time was markedly reduced at the expense of a small reduction in yield compared with the step gradient (44.4 % for plot I and 49.2 % for plot II). The efficiency of the separation by nonlinear concave gradients, for which the pure target enantiomer can be eluted with a shallow modifier gradient, whereas the unresolved fraction with a steep gradient, lies between the linear and step gradients.

In general, the benefit of usage of gradient elution depends on the separation problem, i.e.: on the isotherm range (loading conditions), ee

Fig. 6. Dependencies of the isotherm parameters on the modifier content in the mobile phase. A) MX, the equilibrium constants K_1^I , K_{hom}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} vs. the MTBE content, B) MTSO, the equilibrium constants K_1^I , K_{hom}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} vs. the i -PrOH content, C) MX, q^m vs. the MTBE content. Symbols – experimental data, lines – empirical functional dependencies (Table 2).

of the mixture to be processed and the extent of peak tailing. For example, in the case of the MTSO enantiomeric mixture of $ee = 50\%$ separated with the linear gradient (Fig. 8) the yield improved from 52 to 66 % compared with the isocratic separation of the same mixture eluted in similar time (e.g., 1 % v/v i -PrOH, Fig. 4A). Nevertheless, after each gradient run the column needs re-equilibration, whose duration depends on the modifier adsorption properties. Therefore, the mobile phase composition for isocratic elution or the shape of modifier gradient shall

Table 2

Empirical dependencies of the isotherm coefficients on the modifier concentration ϕ % v/v. The parameter δ determines the difference between K_{hom}^{II} and K_{het}^{II} .

Modifier	Equation
MX	$K_1^I = 0.3906 + 5311 \exp(-0.1506\phi)$
	$K_{hom}^{II} = \delta[-0.2239 + 7.332 \exp(-0.02929\phi)]$
	$K_{het}^{II} = (1 - \delta)[-0.2239 + 7.332 \exp(-0.02929\phi)]$
	$\delta = 0.3413 + 6.889 \times 10^{-4}\phi$
	$q^m = 34.00 - 3.4478 \times 10^{-5} \exp(0.1247\phi)$
MTSO	$K_1^I = 0.1473 + 4.993 \times 10^{-21} \exp(0.4743\phi)$
	$K_{hom}^{II} = \delta[0.1932 + 4.746 \times 10^{-6} \exp(0.1181\phi)]$
	$K_{het}^{II} = (1 - \delta)[0.1932 + 4.746 \times 10^{-6} \exp(0.1181\phi)]$
	$\delta = [0.4341 - 1.227 \times 10^{-26} \exp(0.5863\phi)]$
	$q^m = 68$ (averaged for different modifier concentrations)

Fig. 7. Individual profiles of enantiomers in gradient elution, $V_{in} = 0.09$ mL, $C_{inj} = 60$ mg mL⁻¹, $ee = 50\%$. A) MX, the mobile phase n -hexane/MTBE: step gradient: $\phi_{MTBE} = 60\% - 100\% \text{ v/v}$, $Q = 1$ mL min⁻¹, B) MTSO, the mobile phase MTBE/ i -PrOH: step gradient: $\phi_{i-PrOH} = 0\% - 25\% \text{ v/v}$, $Q = 2$ mL min⁻¹. Symbols – experimental data for the step gradient, dotted line (plot B) – experimental data for the isocratic elution at $\phi_{i-PrOH} = 0\%$, solid line – simulations.

be optimized according to the requirements for the performance indicators, such as: product purity, yield and productivity.

5. Conclusions

The SDE-driven separation of nonracemic mixtures of enantiomers of

Fig. 8. Simulation of the individual profiles of the MTSO enantiomers in gradient elution, $V_{in} = 0.09$ mL, $C_{inj} = 60$ mg mL⁻¹, $Q = 2$ mL min⁻¹, the mobile phase, plot I - linear gradient with the slope ϕ_{i-PrOH} 1% per min., plot II - step gradient: $\phi_{i-PrOH} = 0\%$ - 25% v/v.

two chiral compounds, i.e., MX and MTSO, was performed on an achiral silica-based column. The target product of the separation was the more abundant enantiomer in the mixtures, i.e., *R*-MX or *S*-MTSO. The mobile phases used for the elution were composed of a weak solvent or its mixture with a strong solvent, i.e., the mobile phase modifier. For the elution of MX, a mixture of *n*-hexane and MTBE as the modifier was used, while MTSO was eluted with a mixture of MTBE and *i*-PrOH as the modifier. To determine the influence of the modifier concentration on the extent of the SDE effect, thus on the separation selectivity, the separation of the pairs of enantiomers was performed in isocratic mode at different compositions of the mobile phase. Decrease in the modifier concentration improved the separation yield, but caused an increase of the elution time, e.g., for the enantiomeric mixtures of 50% *ee*, about a tenfold increase in the *R*-MX yield corresponded to a fivefold increase in its retention time, and an approximately twofold increase in the *S*-MTSO yield corresponded to a threefold increase in its retention time. The yield gain increased with increasing *ee* of the mixture. To make a tradeoff between the yield improvement and the extension of the separation time, the fraction containing pure target product was eluted with the weak solvent, whereas the unresolved fraction was eluted with a step increase in the elution strength of the mobile phase, i.e., by increase in the modifier concentration.

To describe the separation process, a model of the column dynamics was used. The model was used to predict the effectiveness of the gradient elution for different gradient shapes. The results obtained indicate that the gradient shape can be adjusted to find the best compromise between the separation selectivity and the process duration.

Moreover, to further improve the separation yield, unresolved fraction containing both enantiomers might be subsequently processed by CCh. In CCh the mixture can be partially resolved to restore the initial *ee* level, and then recycled to SDE-ACh. This would allow partial replacement of CCh by SDE-ACh, thus reducing overall separation costs. That issue will be tackled in a separate study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patrycja Mruc: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Maksymilian Olbrycht:** Data curation, Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology. **Markiian Korbetskyy:** Data curation, Investigation. **Dorota Antos:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

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